

PHONETICS IS A FUNDAMENTAL ASPECT OF ENGLISH LINGUISTICS.

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ABSTRACT. This article covers the phonetics of the English language, focusing on proper pronunciation, the comprehension of English sounds, and how letters combine to form sounds and words.

KEY WORDS: phonetics, English language, pronunciation, letter combinations, sounds.

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqola ingliz tilining fonetikasini o'z ichiga oladi, to'g'ri talaffuz, ingliz tovushlarini tushunish va harflar tovushlar va so'zlarni hosil qilish uchun qanday birlashadi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: fonetika, ingliz tili, talaffuz, harf birikmalari, tovushlar.

АННОТАЦИЯ. В этой статье рассматривается фонетика английского языка с упором на правильное произношение, понимание английских звуков и то, как буквы объединяются в звуки и слова.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: фонетика, английский язык, произношение, сочетание букв, звуки.

INTRODUCTION. The quality of the English language and accurate pronunciation of words and sentences rely on a solid understanding of phonetic principles. Proper pronunciation is crucial for knowing which parts of a sentence should be emphasized with stress and which should remain unstressed. Some English words are pronounced differently from how they are written, as letter combinations often form phonemes that may differ from those familiar to native Russian speakers. Regular speech practice and a grasp of English phonetics will help us speak clearly, minimize the typical Russian accent, and communicate effectively with English speakers.

METHODOLOGY. This article employs a descriptive methodology to explore the phonetics of the English language, focusing on the pronunciation of consonants and vowels, intonation patterns, and stress types. It synthesizes existing linguistic theories and practical examples to illustrate the significance of phonetics in language acquisition. The analysis is supported by examples that highlight key concepts, aiming to provide a clear understanding of the role phonetics plays in effective communication and the mastery of English pronunciation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The English language is used in different countries of the world, and each of them has its own characteristics, including phonetic ones. To make it easier to understand the phonetic features of the language, you need to understand the principle of the formation of sounds and speech organs.

The vocal cords are essential in sound production, as their vibrations generate the voice. The tongue, particularly its front part, plays a significant role in articulating sounds, especially consonants. The middle and back sections of the tongue, though less mobile, are involved in forming vowel sounds. The hard palate aids in producing voiceless sounds with the help of the alveolar ridge. The soft palate, where the uvula is located, directs the airflow. The oral cavity is also crucial, as exhaled air passes through it, forming nasal sounds like [m], [n], [ŋ], as well as oral sounds, which include all other phonemes.

To produce sounds, air must be exhaled from the lungs through the glottis, located between the vocal cords. When the vocal cords are tense, voiced sounds and vowels are created, while relaxed vocal cords produce voiceless sounds. The diaphragm, bronchi, lungs, and trachea act as the driving force behind sound production. Most sounds are shaped in the oral cavity.

Voice intonation is the key element in conveying meaning in English. It is shaped by a combination of pitch, rhythm, tempo, and phrase stress. There are two primary types of intonation in English:

1. Rising tone: This indicates that the statement is incomplete. It is frequently used in lists and questions. The intonation gradually rises from the first stressed syllable to the last.

Examples:

This room has a table, chairs, and a large window?

You can bring my coat?

Did you go shopping?

Sentences with mixed, rising-falling intonations are categorized separately, typically occurring when expressing emotions. Intonation shifts can happen both within a phrase or even within a single word.

Examples:

No! – No! (Expressing disbelief: "It can't be!")

That's excellent. – This is excellent! (Expressing excitement or approval)

Everything can be! – Everything can be! (Conveying surprise or realization)

2. Falling tone: This is used in declarative and affirmative sentences to express judgments, complete thoughts, or facts. It is also typical in imperative sentences.

Examples:

We found a beautiful house. – We found a beautiful house!

Good health to all! – Good health to all!

Go home! – Go home!

Additionally, there are various types of stress in English that affect meaning and emphasis within sentences.

Stress in English can be categorized into verbal, logical, and phrasal stress:

1. Verbal stress: This refers to emphasizing one syllable in a word. In phonetic transcription, the [ˈ] symbol is placed before the stressed syllable. Verbal stress is important for correct pronunciation and distinguishing between different parts of speech.

Examples:

present [pri:ˈsent] – to present (verb)

present [ˈpreznt] – a presentation or gift (noun)

2. Phrasal stress: This emphasizes key parts of a sentence, highlighting important words to convey meaning more effectively.

Examples:

He's a fast learner. – He learns quickly.

What 'happened? – What happened?

Both types of stress guide correct pronunciation and interpretation.

3. Logical stress: This is the most flexible and unpredictable type of stress, as it highlights words the speaker wishes to emphasize for meaning or contrast.

Example:

She did that! – She did it! (emphasizing that she did it, not someone else).

Reading vowels in open and closed syllables:

In English, there are 6 vowels, and depending on their combinations, they can produce 20 different sounds. The way vowels are pronounced depends on the type of syllable they appear in:

- Open syllable: A syllable that ends with a vowel or a silent "e."
The vowel in an open syllable is pronounced as it is in the alphabet.

Example: make [meɪk]

- Closed syllable: A syllable where the vowel is followed by one or more consonants. In this case, the vowel typically conveys a short sound.

Example: cat [kæt] – a cat.

Consonant Sounds in the English Alphabet

To achieve accurate English pronunciation, it's essential to understand how English sounds are articulated, as well as the words in which they occur. Regular

speech practice is equally important, as it involves grasping how English sentences are structured intonationally, which parts are stressed or unstressed, and other phonetic features of the language.

When pronouncing each sound of the English alphabet, various articulators such as the lips, tongue, and other speech organs are involved. English phonetics offers foundational knowledge for beginners to master the correct pronunciation of letters and sounds.

Consonant sounds in English, which outnumber vowel sounds, are categorized into different groups. The first group is known as plosive or explosive consonants, characterized by a specific pronunciation method: the lips are completely closed and then released suddenly.

Examples of plosive sounds include:

- p
- b
- t
- d
- k
- g

Understanding these consonant sounds is crucial for clear and accurate English pronunciation.

Understanding the pronunciation of consonants in English is generally easier than that of vowels. Although English has more consonants than vowels, many of them have counterparts in Russian, making them less challenging for Russian speakers to learn.

In English phonetics, stressed syllables typically occur at regular intervals. When unstressed syllables are present in smaller numbers than stressed ones, they require faster pronunciation.

The falling tone is significant in both narrative and imperative sentences. In business and everyday communication, all affirmative sentences usually end with a drop in voice tone. Conversely, the rising tone indicates uncertainty or doubt and is often used in lists. Unlike the Russian rising tone, English intonation rises at the end of a sentence.

For beginners, many English words may seem unusual to pronounce. However, it's important not to get discouraged, as mastering a standard British accent takes time and practice. In conversations with foreigners, perfect pronunciation is less critical than articulate speech and the ability to comprehend the speaker, as English serves as a language of international communication.

CONCLUSION. For a thorough study of any foreign language, including English, a comprehensive approach is essential, where each element contributes to the overall degree of language acquisition. One crucial aspect of linguistics is English phonetics, which plays a significant role in language learning, particularly for those aiming to understand and articulate their thoughts correctly.

It's important to recognize that language learning involves the establishment of rules that gradually evolve into systems. Therefore, all aspects of the language should be studied systematically, without unnecessary doubts or questions. This holistic approach will facilitate a deeper understanding and more effective use of the language

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